

Squamous cells carcinoma at perineal region of horse: Clinical Report of two cases

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ABSTRACT

15 years old Marwari Skewbald and 8 years white colour mares were presented with tumourous hard and proliferative growth (ulcerated) at perineal region and difficulty in urination. The mass had been growing for the past 3-4 month. On physical examination, there was ulcerated hard mass pressurizing the vulvar region and muscular area of perineal and groin region; area around the tumour was very tense, proliferative and ulcerative. After through physical examination animals were prepared for the surgery. Epidural anaesthesia was given at intercoccygeal space using 2% lignocaine hcl after sedation using combination of xylazine hydrochloride @ 0,6 mg/kg b.wt and butorphanol tartrate @ 0.1 mg/kg b.wt. Intravenously. Curvilinear incision was given and tumourous growth was resected from its base with simultaneously controlling hemorrhages. Tumour samples were collected in 10% formaline solution for histopathological examination. Postoperatively mares weres given inj intacef-Tazo 10mg/kg I/V for 7 days and Inj Flunixin 1.1mg/kg I/M for 3days Daily antiseptic dressing was done until suture removal. Histopathological examination revealed the marked formation of horny pearls suggestive of squamous cells carcinoma. The animalswere fully recovered and any postoperative complication and recurrence was not observed upto three months postoperatively.

Key words-Mares, Squamous cells carcinoma, Perineal region and Horny pearls

Introduction

Squamous cell carcinomas (SCC) are common neoplasm in equines along with melanomas and sarcoids (Singh *et al.*, 2015; Paolis, *et al.*, 2024). It is an invasive skin neoplasm that can originate in several regions, with a predisposition for areas with less skin pigmentation or without hair (Taylor and Haldorson, 2012). Secondary bacterial contamination can happen because it is a cutaneous tumour and therefore it is possible to observe the presence of purulent content on its surface (Ramos *et al.*, 2007). SCC is the second most common cutaneous mass in horses that affects mucocutaneous junctions or external genitalia; Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) accounts for approximately 20% of all equine mucocutaneous (MC) tumours and continues to present a therapeutic challenge to practitioners. (Taylor and Haldorson, 2012). Mucocutaneous squamous cell carcinoma (MC-SCC) is the second most common skin tumour of the horse (Valentine 2006; Theon *et al.* 2007). This report describes the diagnosis and treatment of squamous cells carcinoma at perineal region in two mares.

Case history and Presentation

15 year sold Marwari Skewbald and 8 years white colour mares were presented with tumourous hard and proliferative growth (Ulcerated) at perineal region and difficulty in urination. The mass had been growing for the past 3-4 months in both the cases. On clinical examination, there was ulcerated hard mass at muco-cutaneous junction pressurizing the vulvar and muscular area of groin region; Area around the tumour was very tense (Fig-01) and uneven proliferative (Fig-2).

Fig-01 /Case-01A.Hard mass at perineal region **B.** Curviinear incision **C,** Suturing after excision of tumorous growth

Fig-02/Case-02A.Hard mass at perineal region **B.** Curviinear incision **C,** Suturing after excision of tumorous growth

Surgical Treatment

Premedication

Both the horses were fasted for 12 hrs and were administered with inj. Tetanus toxoid (1500 I.U.) intramuscularly aseptically prior to surgery. The horse was pre-medicated with inj. xylazine (1.1 mg/kg body weight) and inj. butorphanol (0.01mg/kg body weight), intravenously. Perineal region was desensitized with epidural administration of 2% lignocaine hydrochloride.

Surgical Procedure

Site was prepared antiseptically, curvilinear Incision was given ventral side of anus extending dorso-ventrally beside of external vulvar lips. Dissection carried out subcutaneously and deep inside to the tumorous growth and resected from its base with simultaneously controlling hemorrhages. Tumour sample was collected in 10% formaline solution for histopathological examination. Postoperatively horses were given Inj intacef-tazo 10mg/kg I/V for 7 days Inj flunixin 1.1mg/kg I/M for 3days Daily antiseptic dressing was done until suture removal.

Truss to Restrict the Movement of Tail

The animals were fully recovered and any postoperative complication and recurrence was not observed upto three months postoperatively. Histopathological examination revealed the squamous cells carcinoma.

Histopathological slide showing

The neoplastic squamous epithelial cells invaded deep dermis in the form of thick cellular cellular islands and irregular cords composed of concentric layers of squamous cells with keratinization towards the centers forming keratin pearl and cell nests which are characteristics of Squamus cells carcinoma.

Histopathological slide showing neoplastic proliferation of the stratified squamous epithelium and marked formation of horny pearls (arrows) characterizing a squamous cell carcinoma.

Postoperative Photographs-

Case-02 after 05 days

after 10 days

after 30 days

Discussion

The Vulvar region has the characteristics lesions as hard mass which can be ulcerated or proliferative upto the vaginal vestibule and wounds which do not show the healing (van den Top *et al.*, 2011), these finding have been observed in the present study. According to Taylor and Haldorson (2012), only about 13% of SCC cases in horses involve external genitalia. When occurring at the vulva, they usually take a proliferative form, penetrating deep into the surrounding tissues, reaching into the vaginal

vestibule (Smith *et al.*, 2009). Cases of lesions located on the skin of the labia usually have the form of demarcated, ulcerative tumors (Hedau *et al.*, 2017). It is a fairly rare malignant tumor in horses that appears on the skin, on the border between the skin and mucosa, and on nonpigmented mucous membranes, but malignancy of SCC has been established in many cases as compare to other skin tumos such as sarcoid and fibroma (Bharti *et al.*, 2020; Santos *et.al.*, 2022). Squamous cells carcinoma, most commonly affects non-pigmented skin and muco-cutaneous junctions, such as eyelids and external genitalia; on the penis and prepuce in older stallions and geldings, but it has also been described in horses in the nasal cavity, mouth, larynx, nasal sinuses, vulva and vagina (Bharti, *et.al.*, 2013; Ras *et al.*, 2020; Paolis,*et. al.*, 2024). Development of SCC also has been associated with the papillomavirus infection at the genitalia of horses (Kawanishi *et al.*, 2021. Apart from the different clinical observations histopathological findings are the conclusive in the diagnosis of squamous cells carcinoma which is characterized by the neoplastic proliferation of the stratified squamous epithelium and marked formation of horny pearls as observed in both the cases In both the cases granulation and epithelization was observed continuously without any infection and both the cases showed the uneventful recovery and recurrence did not observed upto the three months follow up.

Conclusion

Early diagnosis/detection and appropriate surgical removal/excision/resection of tumor should be done to prevent recurrence and invasion to the surrounding healthy tissue by the carcinogenic cells.Periodic examination for assessment of the effectiveness of surgical treatment and early detection of any possible recurrence.

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